

NEW SMARANDACHE ALGEBRAIC STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Generally in R^3 any plane with equation $x + y + z = a$, where a is nonzero number, is not a linear space under the usual vector addition and scalar multiplication. If we define new algebraic operations on the plane $x + y + z = a$ it will become a linear space in R^3 . The additive identity of this linear space has nonzero components.

1. The plane $x + y + z = a$ touches the x -axis at point $A (a, 0, 0)$, y -axis at point $B (0, a, 0)$ and z -axis at point $C (0, 0, a)$. Take triangle ABC as a fixed equilateral triangle known as "triangle of reference."

From any point P in its plane draw perpendiculars PM , PN and PL to AC , AB and BC respectively. Let $\mathcal{L}(PM) = p_1$, $\mathcal{L}(PN) = p_2$ and $\mathcal{L}(PL) = p_3$. These p_1 , p_2 and p_3 are called the trilinear coordinator of point P [Loney 1, Smith 2, Sen 3].

The coordinate p_1 is positive if P and the vertex B of the triangle are on the same side of AC and p_1 is negative if P and B are on the opposite sides of AC . So for the other coordinates p_2 and p_3 .

2. Length of each side of the triangle is $\sqrt{2} |a| = b$ (say).
 $1/2 \cdot b \cdot p_1 + 1/2 \cdot b \cdot p_2 + 1/2 \cdot b \cdot p_3 = 1/2 \cdot b \cdot \sqrt{3} / 2 \cdot b$

$$p_1 + p_2 + p_3 = \sqrt{3} / 2 \cdot b = k \text{ (say).}$$

The trilinear coordinates p_1, p_2, p_3 of any point P in the plane whether it is within the triangle or outside the triangle ABC satisfy the relation

$$p_1 + p_2 + p_3 = k \tag{2.1}$$

Thus trilinear coordinates of points A, B and C are $(0, 0, k)$, $(k, 0, 0)$ and $(0, k, 0)$ respectively. Trilinear coordinates of the centroid of triangle are $(k/3, k/3, k/3)$.

3. Now the plane $x + y + z = a$ is a set T of all points p whose trilinear coordinates p_1, p_2, p_3 satisfy the relation $p_1 + p_2 + p_3 = k$.

Let $p = (p_1, p_2, p_3)$ and $q = (q_1, q_2, q_3)$ be in T .

$$\text{By usual addition } p + q = (p_1 + q_1, p_2 + q_2, p_3 + q_3) \notin T, \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{since } (p_1 + q_1) + (p_2 + q_2) + (p_3 + q_3) = (p_1 + p_2 + p_3) + (q_1 + q_2 + q_3) = 2k \quad (3.2)$$

$$\text{By usual scalar multiplication by } \alpha, \alpha p = (\alpha p_1, \alpha p_2, \alpha p_3) \notin T, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\text{since } \alpha p_1 + \alpha p_2 + \alpha p_3 = \alpha (p_1 + p_2 + p_3) = \alpha k. \quad (3.4)$$

In view of (3.1), (3.2), (3.3) and (3.4) the set T is not closed with respect to the usual vector addition and scalar multiplication. Hence it can not become a linear space.

4. Now we shall prove, by defining following new algebraic operations, T is a linear space in which components of additive identity are nonzero.

4.1 **Definition** Let $p = (p_1, p_2, p_3)$ & $q = (q_1, q_2, q_3)$ be in T .

We define :

a. **Equality :**

$$p = q \text{ if and only if } p_1 = q_1, p_2 = q_2, p_3 = q_3.$$

b. **Sum :**

$$p + q = (-k/3 + p_1 + q_1, -k/3 + p_2 + q_2, -k/3 + p_3 + q_3)$$

c. **Multiplication by real numbers :**

$$\alpha p = ((1 - \alpha)k/3 + \alpha p_1, (1 - \alpha)k/3 + \alpha p_2, (1 - \alpha)k/3 + \alpha p_3) \\ (\alpha \text{ real})$$

d. **Difference :**

$$p - q = p + (-1)q.$$

e. **Zero vector (centroid of the triangle):**

$$0 = (k/3, k/3, k/3).$$

- 5.1 To every pair of elements p and q in T there corresponds an element $p + q$, in such a way that

$$p + q = q + p \quad \text{and} \quad p + (q + r) = (p + q) + r.$$

$$p + 0 = p \quad \text{for every } p \in T.$$

To each $p \in T$ there exists a unique element $-p$ such that $p + (-p) = 0$

T is an abelian group with respect to vector addition.

- 5.2 For every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ and $p, q \in T$ we have

$$\text{i) } \alpha (\beta p) = (\alpha \beta) p$$

$$\text{ii) } \alpha (p + q) = \alpha p + \alpha q,$$

$$\text{iii) } (\alpha + \beta) p = \alpha p + \beta p$$

$$\text{iv) } 1p = p.$$

Therefore T is a real linear space.

- Remark .1. The real number k is related with the position of the plane $x+y+z= a$ in R^3
2. There are infinite number of linear spaces of above kind in R^3

References.

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